

Financing Public Libraries in Nigeria: Alternatives Sources to Government

Nigerian nation is unstable as a result of economic, political and social conditions. Nigeria Public Libraries are also facing similar crisis. The direct consequence of this is that the quality of Library, materials, facilities and services has deteriorated. The extent to which the Nigerian Public Library can go in terms of nature, operation, function and services depends on funds available to the library. In the last decade, public libraries have been in critical conditions that warrant the design of alternatives so that they can survive. The path to the survival of Nigerian Public Libraries lies in sourcing for funds outside Government coffers.